

Grain quality of some Basmati genotypes

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Grain size and shape must be considered in germplasm improvement along with milling percent because they largely determine the market acceptability of milled rice. Long, slender rice grain fetches a high price on the international market. Elongation of rice grains during cooking is one of the unique features of Basmati rice.

Some of the key Basmati traits—slenderness, translucency, and aroma—are simply inherited, but linear grain elongation follows a complex pattern of inheritance. In thaladi 1995 (September-October-January-February), we evaluated 23 rice genotypes along with two checks, Taraori Basmati and Pusa Basmati, for hulling, milling, head rice recovery, breadth, length-breadth ratio (L/B), and elongation ratio for rice quality improvement. A randomized block design with three replications was used on 12-m² plots and each genotype transplanted with 20- × 15-cm spacing.

Brown rice percent among the genotypes ranged from 70.38 to 87.16% and milled rice percent ranged from 56.86 to 80.25% (see table). The highest for brown rice (87.16%) and the highest for milled rice (80.25%) were recorded for the HKR90-414 genotype. Head rice recovery ranged from 25.01 to 53.59%. The genotype RP3138-42-11-7-1 had the highest head rice recovery of 53.59%, followed by RP3121-14-70-2 (43.61%), which are higher than the check (Taraori Basmati, 27.57%). Twelve out of 23 genotypes approached the checks in kernel length and L/B. The genotypes RP3138-42-11-7-4, RP3138-78-25-11-4, and RP3138-56-11-9-3 showed more than double the grain elongation during cooking and was higher than Pusa Basmati. ■

Grain quality characteristics of some rice genotypes at TRRI, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India. 1995 thaladi.

Genotype	Brown rice (%)	Milled rice (%)	Head rice recovery (%)	Milled grain			Cooked grain length	Elongation ratio
				Length	Breadth	L/B		
UPR1071-21-1-1	81.31	73.36	41.01	6.64	1.55	4.28	10.50	1.58
RP3238-33-15-7	84.16	76.57	32.85	7.20	1.71	4.21	11.10	1.54
RP-ST-328	75.85	68.17	34.90	6.68	1.65	4.10	11.70	1.75
HKR90-421	82.54	72.95	37.13	6.93	1.64	4.22	12.30	1.77
HKR90-404	80.43	70.74	41.31	6.81	1.76	3.86	11.10	1.62
HKR90-403	84.26	79.46	25.04	6.83	1.72	3.97	13.00	1.90
HKR90-413	84.31	79.42	25.01	7.67	1.58	4.85	12.30	1.60
HKR90-414	87.16	80.25	27.61	7.73	1.62	4.77	12.00	1.55
BK843-2	80.14	56.86	25.39	7.06	1.63	4.33	11.80	1.67
BK843-7	80.55	70.66	28.69	7.30	1.62	4.51	12.50	1.71
NDR6017	82.49	73.37	41.16	6.82	1.66	4.10	11.10	1.62
HKR91-405	75.78	68.12	39.10	6.18	1.55	4.10	12.00	1.94
HKR91-406	78.12	70.41	32.45	7.91	1.74	4.55	12.90	1.63
HKR91-408	85.16	74.76	33.94	7.29	1.64	4.45	11.90	1.63
RP3138-42-11-7-1	72.97	69.34	53.59	6.92	1.69	4.09	12.30	1.77
RP3138-42-11-7-4	77.78	68.27	26.45	6.88	1.59	4.32	15.30	2.22
RP3138-78-20-9-2	80.08	70.62	29.94	6.97	1.56	4.47	12.70	1.82
RP3138-78-25-11-4	75.65	64.71	26.44	7.13	1.62	4.40	15.50	2.17
HKR92-401	84.69	75.64	33.05	7.71	1.61	4.79	12.80	1.66
RP3121-14-70-2	84.67	75.19	43.61	7.45	1.61	4.63	11.90	1.59
RP3138-56-11-9-3	78.07	67.93	26.81	6.89	1.66	4.15	14.70	2.13
RP3138-60-9-6-6	78.28	70.01	26.04	7.16	1.64	4.37	13.20	1.84
UPR-BS-92-4	78.03	66.49	26.68	7.48	1.62	4.62	13.30	1.77
Taraori Basmati	70.38	64.83	27.57	7.52	1.67	4.50	13.90	1.83
Pusa Basmati	85.18	72.17	26.06	7.64	1.64	4.66	14.50	1.89
Mean	80.33	71.53	32.47	7.15	1.64	4.31	12.60	1.76
CV	2.72	5.24	3.52	0.80	5.78	0.64	1.64	0.18

Physicochemical properties of japonica and indica waxy rice

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Waxy rice is important for dessert and sweet products. Five japonica and five indica varieties were tested during 1996 to compare their physicochemical properties. The varieties were Sinseonchalbyeo, Buklukbanna, Wonsanchalbyeo, Iri309, and Hwaseonchalbyeo (japonica) and Hankangchalbyeo, Iri352, IR29, IR65, and RD6 (indica).

Alkali spreading values at 1.7 and 1.4% KOH, protein, and Mg content were not significantly different except for amylose ($p < 0.05$), K content

($p < 0.05$), and Mg/K ($p < 0.01$) between japonica and indica milled waxy rices (see table). Hardness of japonica (9.83 kg) of cooked waxy rice was higher than that of indica (6.95 kg), but the other texturometer measurements were not different. The results indicated that the hardness of cooked waxy rice is an important eating quality indicator of japonica and indica waxy rice.

The water-binding capacity was significant between japonica and indica waxy rice starches ($p < 0.01$), 196 and 183%, respectively (see table). Gel consistency, which ranges from 78 to 88 mm, is soft and not significant between them. The transmittance and swelling power of japonica were lower and higher than those of indica waxy rice starch in the slope of the curves below 70 °C. The peak ($p < 0.05$), breakdown ($p < 0.050$), and setback ($p < 0.01$) amylograph viscosities were significantly dif-